

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

STRENGTHENING DEMOCRATIC PEDAGOGY THROUGH THE CRITICAL CHANGE LAB MODEL

POLICY BRIEF

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The **Critical ChangeLab (CCLAB)** project is a research and innovation initiative funded under the European Commission's Horizon Europe programme. Emerging as a response to growing concerns across Europe about young people's increasing detachment from democratic life, its main objective is to design, implement, and evaluate a flexible pedagogical model, the **CCLAB Model**, that empowers young people as active citizens.

Through an **iterative design process** based on three Participatory Action Research (PAR) cycles with youth and educators, implemented in more than 76 labs across 21 countries, the model has been refined and tested to generate solid evidence of its impacts and limitations.

This policy brief synthesises the key insights derived from the process evaluation of the model, which unfolded across the three PAR cycles (2024–2025), each followed by redesign iterations that strengthened its pedagogical and methodological foundation.

THE CRITICAL CHANGELAB MODEL

The CCLAB is grounded in several **core principles**: it is youth-centered, participatory, oriented toward transformation, and relies on artistic and creative methods to foster inquiry, critical reflection, and action on emerging eco-social issues. The model is structured into three interconnected blocks:

- **Question & Analyze**, where young people identify eco-social issues that concern them and explore them through participatory inquiry.
- **Envision & Act**, where they imagine alternatives to the current reality and design/implement actions aimed at change.
- **Reflect**, collective reflection on the process, its meanings, and outcomes.

Through this approach, CCLAB aims to develop **four core competences** for critical citizenship: (1) critical understanding of the world; (2) creative and imaginative capacity; (3) democratic disposition; (4) transformative agency.

KEY INSIGHTS

1. YOUTH PERSPECTIVES ON CRITICAL CITIZENSHIP

- Young people often approach eco-social issues from **personal and local experiences**, strongly tied to emotional connections with their immediate environment.
- They show strong awareness of **contemporary challenges**, but face difficulties linking individual experiences to **systemic and structural dynamics**.
- A **scarcity of democratic experiences** in schools undermines opportunities to practice meaningful participation. This highlights the need to move from teaching democracy in

theory to creating participatory spaces where students actively engage and influence decisions.

- There is resistance to socially engaged projects perceived as lacking real impact, leading to frustration and risks of disengagement.
- A key challenge lies in **imagining alternative futures**: while they can criticise the present, envisioning transformative possibilities beyond collapse or repetition of the status quo proved difficult.

2. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES AND LEARNING PROCESSES

- Experiential, art-based and participatory research methods proved effective in connecting abstract democratic concepts to young peoples lived realities. Strategies such as visual expression, performative activities, participatory research, debates, and community-based projects helped foster critical reflection, imagination, and a stronger sense of agency.

3. INSTITUTIONAL CHALLENGES

- Time constraints limit sustained engagement. Institutional schedules and curriculum deadlines tend to prioritize content over experience, leaving students insufficient time for deep reflection and collaboration in creative and participatory processes, thus causing superficial engagement, frustration, and limited participation.
- Rigid school structures and hierarchical relations, within classrooms and in the whole educational system, often reduce the scope and opportunities for youth participation.
- Democratic education requires systemic reform to move beyond theory towards an applied everyday student experience. A way of achieving this is by validating diverse knowledge and linking curriculum to student realities.
- Participatory Action Research projects, such as the CCLAB, require institutional support to guarantee its sustainability, so that any significative and transformative change regarding democratic education becomes part of the school culture and to allow scaling, so that any method that has been proven relevant and succesful for engaging youth with ecosocial issues may be extrapolated in other similar contexts.

POLICY IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of the Critical ChangeLab project underline the urgent need for **systemic changes** in educational environments to promote democratic competences among young people. Evidence shows that youth are willing and capable of engaging with eco-social and democratic challenges, but their potential is often limited by institutional constraints and lack of meaningful participation opportunities. The **CCLAB model** demonstrates that when democracy is lived as an everyday practice, supported by creative and participatory methods, it fosters stronger civic engagement and critical competences.

1. EDUCATIONAL POLICIES

Transform learning environments into everyday democratic spaces

- Encourage schools and non-formal learning environments to treat everyday spaces as democratic arenas where youth voices are valued.
- Promote policies that embed democratic culture in schools beyond curricular content.
- Establish real mechanisms for student participation in institutional decision-making.
- Empower school communities to jointly shape learning priorities and activities.
- Avoid symbolic or tokenistic involvement. Create conditions where students' contributions genuinely influence outcomes.

Curriculum design

- Embed epistemological pluralism by recognizing diverse ways of knowing, including emotional, artistic, embodied, and experiential.
- Connect abstract concepts with students' lived realities.
- Promote interdisciplinary approaches that link social, ecological, and historical issues.
- Recognize imagination as a core competence for future-oriented learning.
- Incorporate participatory research methodologies in curricula.
- Adjust timetables to allow slower, more reflective processes.

Sustainability and institutional practices:

- Support continuity of socially engaged projects across education cycles. This means offering regularly participatory action research experiences for different educational stages and that the outcomes of these actions can revert into participants' care and engagement in these processes.
- Enable mechanisms that sustain long-term initiatives for students, teachers and the educational community at large.
- Encourage networking and collaboration between schools, communities, and organizations, so that the pedagogical moment that includes putting ideas into action finds concrete exchange outputs and acquires local relevance.
- Foster partnerships between schools and community actors to ensure that student-led projects have real impact, visibility, and continuity beyond the classroom.
- Make processes and results visible to broader communities.

Teacher training

- Establish professional development programs focused on inviting teachers to adopt critical, creative, participatory, and intersectional pedagogies.

2 YOUTH POLICIES

- Recognize **young people** as **agents of change**, not passive beneficiaries.
- Avoid **adult-centric narratives** that minimize youth voices.
- Create **spaces** where young people can **imagine and build alternative futures**.
- Include **youth** in the **design of public policies** that affect their lives.
- Support projects that **connect young people** with **their local environment** and community actors

CONCLUSION

The Critical ChangeLab model offers a tested, adaptable framework for strengthening democratic pedagogy. Its evidence shows that democratic competences flourish when learning is grounded in lived experience, creative expression, and genuine participation. Educational and youth policies must now take the next step: embedding these practices structurally to transform schools into everyday democratic spaces and ensuring that young people are recognized as key actors in shaping collective futures. Adopting these recommendations will contribute to building a more inclusive, participatory, and resilient democracy in Europe.

CRITICAL CHANGE LAB

Critical ChangeLab is a three-year long EU funded project that aims to build a resilient European democracy by reinvigorating the relationship between youth and democracy through civic interventions in which young people envision alternative futures for (shared) European democracy, and act on that.

Education

Research

Culture